

Mathematical Description of the Regensburg Model Scenario Types RM 1 – 6

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1 Introduction

The Regensburg Model Scenario Types RM 1 – 6 are used to derive plausible emission paths that meet a certain budget. The emission paths are essentially determined indirectly by assumptions about the trajectory of annual changes. This is the innovative core of the RM Scenario Types.

We pursue two approaches:

1. Determination of the trajectory of the annual rates of change (RM 1 - 5).
2. Determination of a constant annual reduction amount (RM-6).

In the indirect determination of emission paths using annual rates of change with a monotonic trajectory, the following four **basic types** can be distinguished:¹

- (1) Initial less-than-proportional decline in annual rates of change (RM-2, RM-4) ► concave
- (2) Initial more-than-proportional decline in annual rates of change (RM-5) ► convex
- (3) Linear decline in annual rates of change (RM-3) ► linear
- (4) Constant annual rate of change (RM-1) ► constant

The RM Scenario Types are used in our **tools** to derive plausible global or national emission paths.

The **Excel tools** listed in the References can be downloaded from Zenodo (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2026a; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2026b; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025a; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025b). Here is an overview and description of the tools: <http://downloads.save-the-climate.info>.

Here is an overview of our **web applications**: <https://climate-calculator.info>.

2 Constraints to be specified

B	budget for a certain period (budget period); here: 2020 - 2100
E_{BY}	emissions in the base year (BY); here: $BY = 2019$
E_{min}	minimum of emissions in the budget period; a negative value represents the potential for net negative emissions
RR_{SY}	rate of change in the start year in RM 2 – 5; in scenario type RM-2, only a negative value is possible
$TV_{RM\ 1-5}$	threshold at which the method is changed in order to map net negative emissions in a pragmatic way (from this value onwards, a constant annual reduction amount is used)

¹ For positive rates, a **decline** in annual rates of change corresponds to a decline in emissions growth; for negative rates, it corresponds to an increase in the absolute value of reduction rates.

3 Formulae for the Regensburg Model Scenario Types

3.1 Determination of paths via annual rates of change (scenario types RM 1 – 5)

$$E_t = \begin{cases} \max(E_{min}; E_{t-1} * (1 + RR_t)) & \text{for } E_{t-1} > TV^2 \\ \max(E_{min}; E_{t-1} + (E_{t-1} - E_{t-2})) & \text{for } E_{t-1} \leq TV^3 \end{cases}$$

where:

E_t emissions in the year t ; here: 2020 – 2100

The **annual rates of change** in the individual scenario types are based on the following formulae:

name scenario type	formula	basic function type	con-straint	trajectory of the annual rates of change
RM-2-exp ⁴	$RR_t = RR_{t-1} * (1 + a)$	e^x	$a \geq 0$	► concave
RM-4-quadr ⁵	$RR_t = a * (t - (BY + 1))^2 + RR_{BY+1}$	$y = ax^2 + b$	$a \leq 0$	
RM-5-rad ⁶	$RR_t = a * \sqrt{t - (BY + 1) - 0.5} + RR_{BY+1}$	$y = a\sqrt{x} + b$	$a \leq 0$	► convex
RM-3-lin	$RR_t = a * (t - (BY + 1)) + RR_{BY+1} = RR_{t-1} + a$	$y = ax + b$	$a \leq 0$	► linear
RM-1-const	$RR_t = a$	$y = a$	$a \leq 0$	► constant

Table 1: Formulae for the RM Scenario Types 1 - 5⁷

The free parameter a is determined for each scenario type using an iterative solution method so that the budget (B) is met. In the Excel tools, the integrated target value search (“goal seek”) is used for this purpose, which is embedded in a macro⁸ that ensures that the constraint for a is also met.⁹

² "Max" means here, take the larger value. Either E_{min} or E_t (which results from the application of RR_t).

³ "Max" means here, take the larger value. Either E_{min} or E_t (which results from applying the last absolute reduction amount; the emission path is then a straight line).

⁴ In this scenario type, the free parameter a can be called the escalation rate applied to the previous year's annual rate of change. This scenario type can also be represented using the following formula: $RR_{BY+1} * e^{(t-(BY+1))*\ln(1+a)}$.

⁵ Basic function type: $y = ax^2 + b$. The term $[t - (BY + 1)]$ is used as x in a variable transformation to allow calculations with years. For $t = 2020$ the value of the term is 0. The term thus takes the values 0, 1, ..., 80 for the period 2020 - 2100 considered here.

⁶ Basic function type: $y = a\sqrt{x} + b$. The term $[t - (BY + 1) - 0.5]$ is used as x . The correction term 0.5 serves to smooth the trajectory at the beginning (see Chapter 8.1). The term $[t - (BY + 1)]$ represents a variable transformation to allow calculations with years. x thus takes the values 0.5, 1.5, ..., 79.5 in the period 2021 - 2100 considered here.

⁷ In scenario types RM-2, RM-3 and RM-5, the predefined RR_{SY} (see Chapter 2) must be used for $t = SY$. Thus, the equations above hold for $t > BY + 1$ (here: $t > 2020$).

⁸ The macro has been published separately (Wolfsteiner, 2024).

⁹ If no solution can be found with the given framework data, RR_{SY} is varied in the Excel tools and B in the corresponding web apps.

3.2 Determination of paths via annual reduction amount (scenario type RM-6)

$$\text{RM-6-abs: } E_t = \max(E_{min}; E_{t-1} + RA)^{10}$$

The free parameter **RA** (constant annual reduction amount) is determined using an iterative solution method so that the budget (B) is met.¹¹

3.3 Phases for determining the paths

This usually leads to the following **three phases** for determining the paths (see Figure 3 for illustration):¹²

1. Application of the **annual rates of change** (RM 1 - 5) or of the **annual reduction amount** (RM-6).
2. For RM 1 – 5, if $E_{t-1} \leq TV$, the last reduction amount from phase 1 is used as a constant reduction amount until E_{min} is reached. In this phase, the emission path is a straight line.
3. Once E_{min} is reached, annual emissions remain at E_{min} until 2100.

4 Setting the parameters

4.1 Starting rate of change (RR_{SY})

In most tools, the starting rate of change RR_{SY} is set for the first year without actual emissions. Since the starting rate of change is the basis for all subsequent rates of change, it should be based on a normalised value. Years affected by exceptional events should generally not be used as reference years. Instead, RR_{SY} should reflect the underlying trend.

4.2 Minimum value of the emission path (E_{min})

If net negative emissions are allowed ($E_{min} < 0$), the budget may be temporarily exceeded. This overshoot will then be offset by net negative emissions by 2100.

E_{min} is specified in most tools as a percentage of emissions in the base year 2019 (N):

$$E_{min} = E_{BY} * N$$

If N is negative, a temporary overshoot is possible.

See [this](#) paper on the limitations of an overshoot (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025c).

¹⁰ "Max" means here, take the larger value. Either E_{min} or E_t (which results from the application of the constant annual reduction amount: **RA**).

¹¹ We also offer a formula-based solution for the scenario type RM-6 (cf. Wittmann & Wolfsteiner, 2023).

¹² When actual emissions are available after the base year, there is another phase with actual values.

4.3 Thresholds for transition to Phase 2 (TVs)

The *TVs* are calculated in the tools by applying a percentage (*TV%*) to the emissions in the base year:

$$TV_{RM\ 1-5} = TV\%_{RM\ 1-5} * E_{BY}$$

The following values generally produce plausible results, some of which can also be adjusted within the tools:

$$TV\%_{RM-1} = 4.5\% = M_{RM-1}$$

$$TV\%_{RM\ 2-5} = 3.5\% = M_{RM\ 2-5}$$

In principle, however, the higher the potential for net negative emissions, the higher these *TVs* should be in order to obtain a plausible path.¹³

For this reason, some tools allow *TVs* to be derived directly from the potential for net negative emissions:

$$TV\%_{RM\ 1-5} = \begin{cases} \max(-N * (1 + S_{RM\ 1-5}); M_{RM\ 1-5}) & \text{for } E_{min} < 0 \\ M_{RM\ 1-5} & \text{for } E_{min} \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

where *M* denotes the minimum value for *TV%* used in the tools.

Plausible values for *S*, which can also be changed in the tools:

$$S_{RM-1} = 85\%$$

$$S_{RM\ 2-5} = 50\%$$

5 Overview of the RM Scenario Types

basic type (see Chapter 1)	Scenario Type	trajectory of the annual rates of change	basic function type	trajectory of annual reduction amounts	trajectory of the emission paths
(4)	RM-1-const	constant	$y = \text{constant}$	concave	convex
(3)	RM-3-lin	linear	$y = ax + b$	u-shaped	s-shaped (first concave then convex)
(1)	RM-2-exp	concave	$y = e^x$	u-shaped	
	RM-4-quadr		$y = ax^2 + b$	u-shaped	
(2)	RM-5-rad	convex	$y = a\sqrt{x} + b$	u-shaped	
-	RM-6-abs	concave	-	constant	linear

Table 2: RM Scenario Types overview¹⁴

In principle, there are several options for mapping the basic types (1) and (2) using a specific function (see Chapter 8.2 for further examples). However, the results of the functions used in basic types (1) and (2) differ only to a limited extent when the budget is tight. This is also shown by comparing

¹³ If the *TV* is set too low, the path may decline steeply in the rate-based phase and then flatten abruptly once the method switches to a constant annual reduction amount. A higher *TV* reduces this kink by shifting the transition to an earlier stage. As a result, E_{min} is reached earlier, and the third phase, in which annual emissions remain at E_{min} , becomes longer and increasingly important for offsetting a temporary overshoot.

¹⁴ See also Chapter 6 for a graphic illustration of the differences.

the results of RM-2 and RM-4 (cf. Figure 1). Therefore, scenario types RM 1 and RM 3 – 6 cover the range of plausible trajectories well.

For RM-1, with a constant annual reduction rate, and RM-6, with a constant annual reduction amount, the starting rate of change is endogenous. In the other scenario types, RR_{SY} can be specified exogenously at a realistic level.¹⁵

¹⁵ However, only a negative value is possible for the scenario type RM-2.

6 Exemplary annual rates of change and emission paths¹⁶

In the following figures, the RM Scenario Types have been applied to global paths.¹⁷ A global CO₂ budget of 550 Gt for 2020 - 2100 was assumed in Figure 1 and in Figure 2. In Figure 1, the starting rate of change ($RR_{SY} = RR_{2020}$) was set at -0.5% and E_{min} at -0.8 Gt. In Figure 2, a starting rate of change of +1.5% was chosen. In Figure 3, a global CO₂ budget of 400 Gt for 2020 - 2100 was assumed and E_{min} was set at -3.8 Gt ($RR_{SY} = RR_{2020} = +0.5\%$).

Figure 1: RM Scenario Types 1 - 6

¹⁶ The RM Scenario Types can also be explored graphically using our web app: <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>.

¹⁷ Tool used: (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2026a).

Figure 2: RM Scenario Types with positive starting rate of change (RM 3 – 5)

Figure 3: RM Scenario Types with high net negative emissions

7 Choice of a RM Scenario Type

The following questions can play a role in the selection of a scenario type:¹⁸

1. Which annual rates of change are realistic and when?
2. Do initially slowly declining annual rates of change (RM-2/4 and RM-6) place an unjustifiable burden on the future, since they require very high reduction rates later on?¹⁹
3. Could high later reduction rates even make sense because they provide a greater lead time for the necessary investments? The investments could then be aligned more closely with normal investment cycles. However, this requires highly credible climate policy backed by effective instruments.
4. Do initially rapidly declining annual rates of change (RM-3 and RM-5) convey a more credible climate policy that creates planning security for public and private investments in a fossil-free future?

Overall, in many cases, scenario types RM-2 and RM-4 may be particularly realistic, as they allow initially moderate increases in reduction rates. RM-4 has the additional advantage that a positive starting rate of change can also be specified. However, these scenario types require highly credible climate policy and effective instruments so that investments in a fossil-free future are made in time.

¹⁸ Cf. corresponding excursus in (Sargl, et al., 2026) and corresponding chapter in (Wolfsteiner, 2026).

¹⁹ See footnote 1 on the use of the term ‘decline’.

8 Attachment

8.1 Correction term RM-5

Why does the formula for the annual rates of change contain the term **0.5**?

$$RR_t = a * \sqrt{t - (BY + 1) - 0.5} + RR_{BY+1}$$

As shown in Figure 4, the interaction of the weighting factor *a* and the root without the correction term **0.5** in RM-5-rad would result in a relatively large step in the annual rates of change from the first year in the budget period to the second year. The correction term 0.5 smooths this curve.

Figure 4: RM-5 correction term

8.2 Further possible scenario types

- Concave: $RR_t = RR_{BY+1} * e^{a*(t-(BY+1))}$
This variant produces a trajectory that is almost identical to RM-2-exp over the range considered here.
- Convex: $RR_t = a * \ln(t - BY) + RR_{BY+1}$
Figure 5 shows the difference compared with RM-5-rad:

Figure 5: Further scenario type LN

- In addition to monotonic trajectories of annual rates of change, a U-shaped trajectory could also be plausible. This could be based on the assumption that, after ‘harvesting the low-hanging fruit’, reduction rates may have to decline again. However, lead times for reductions, for example in the 2040s, can have the opposite effect: with credible climate policy, early long-term investments may enable a continuous increase in reduction rates.
- A function for the emission path can also be specified directly. See, for example, the corresponding chapters in: Resource Sharing Models - A mathematical description; published on [Zenodo](#) (Wittmann & Wolfsteiner, 2023). In the RM Scenario Types, however, the focus is on the trajectory of annual changes. Focusing on the necessary annual rates of change makes the challenge clearer and facilitates the choice of a meaningful emission path (cf. Chapter 7).

References

- Sargl, M., Wiegand, D., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2026. *Calculation of Paris-compatible emission targets for the six largest emitters with the ESPM*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4764408>
- Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2023. *Resource Sharing Models – A Mathematical Description*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4405448>
- Wolfsteiner, A., 2024. *Macro "goal seek"*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7494168>
- Wolfsteiner, A., 2026. *Berechnung Paris-kompatibler Emissionspfade mit dem ESPM am Beispiel der EU*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5678717>
- Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025a. *Tool for the Calculation of Paris-compatible Global Emission Paths with the RM Scenario Types*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4584562>
- Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025b. *Tool for the Calculation of Paris-compatible National Emission Paths with the Regensburg Model*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5846043>
- Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025c. *Treatment of the topics LUC and net negative emissions in the RM and ESPM tools*. [Online]
Available at: <http://luc.climate-calculator.info>
- Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2026a. *Tool for the Calculation of Emission Paths with the RM Scenario Types*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4568839>
- Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2026b. *Tool for the Calculation of Paris-compatible Emission Paths with the ESPM*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4580310>